

FLOW STATE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN THE FORGING DIE DURING THE MOLDING PROCESS CONTINUED : EFFECTS OF MOLDING TEMPERATURE

Tsuneo HIRAI *, Tsutao KATAYAMA **
and Hiroyuki HAMADA *

** Department of Mechanical Engineering
Doshisha University, Kyoto, Japan*

*** Osaka Prefectural Industrial Research Institute, Sakai, Japan*

Abstract

In the field of composite materials, such as fiber reinforced plastics, the molding process using a matched die is attracting wide attention as a mass production technology. BMC and SMC have been developed for the process, but it seems to have some troubles, especially in the strengthened component parts like a rib. One of them is a surface appearance with central cavity (piping defect) which occurs during the final stages of the molding process. Another one is brittle weakness at the bottom of fin portion caused by a stress concentration in the resin rich fillet part.

In order to prevent these troubles, it is necessary to investigate the flow state of BMC during the molding process. In previous paper the numerical analysis was made for BMC flow as anisotropic pseudo-plastic material, taking into consideration the difference between fluid resistance in normal and parallel direction to the flow.

In this paper to pursuing the flow state the progressive step by step method was used and moreover in the case of taking consideration into the molding temperature the heat conduction equation was added to the governing equations. The results can well be explained the flow state of composite materials and the fundamental data the design of the die was obtained.

1) Introduction

Along with the recent trend of mass production, techniques for hot compression molding of composite materials have been developed, especially, in the field of matched-die molding. However, there seem to be still some problems to be solved for further improvements. Among there, the most serious troubles that frequently happen are the occurrence of surface cavity and of brittle weakness at resin-rich part in the SMC and BMC products. The primary step to solve these two problems is obviously to analyze the flow state of materials during the process.

Since the composite materials are a mixture of the plastic matrix and the reinforcement, it seems probable to think that the data accumulated for the forming of metals which are of homogeneous nature may not be applied to the composite materials. In the previous paper, the flow state of BMC was compared with that of plasticine which shows the homogeneous nature and difference between them was discussed. It is considered that the different characteristics in the flow state of BMC may arise from its heterogeneity and the anisotropy in fiber orientation to the flow direction. The governing equations that are the anisotropic pseudo-plastic equation were presented on an assumption that the fluid resistance in normal direction to the flow differs from that in parallel direction and numerical results obtained with these equations were found to agree well with the experimental results observed at the initial flow state. However the sufficient analysis of the effect of the rib wall on the flow states was not successfully made.

In the actual works the die is pre-heated and this develops the temperature distribution in the materials which results in the complex flow behaviors. As the temperature rises, the viscosity lowers and the materials soften and a certain temperature they begin to harden by a polymerization. Thus the analysis of the flow state must be made on the basis of temperature distribution in the materials caused by the molding temperature. In this paper, an attempt was made to improve the numerical analysis by the progressive step by step method and the molding process where the polymerization might be neglected was analyzed by considering the heat conduction to the materials.

2) Governing equation and its analysis

2-1 Governing equation

Taking into consideration the difference between the fluid resistance in normal and parallel directions to the flow, the flow state of composite materials was analyzed on the basis of anisotropic pseudo-plastic fluid flow. The pseudo-plastic viscosity K_n , in normal direction to the flow, and K_L , in parallel direction, are transformed into K_y and K_x by Eq.(1),

$$\begin{Bmatrix} K_x \\ K_y \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2\theta & \sin^2\theta \\ \sin^2\theta & \cos^2\theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} K_L \\ K_n \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \dots(1)$$

where K_x and K_y are the pseudo-plastic viscosities in x and y directions, respectively. The corresponding viscosity, μ_x and μ_y , are written as

$$\mu_x = \frac{K_x}{3} (\sqrt{4J_2/3})^{n-1}, \quad \mu_y = \frac{K_y}{3} (\sqrt{4J_2/3})^{n-1}. \quad \dots(2)$$

The anisotropic pseudo-plastic and continuity equations which had been shown in the previous paper are then used to analyze the composite materials. These equations are written as follows;

$$\rho u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} - \mu_x \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = 0, \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\rho u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - \mu_y \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} \right) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} = 0, \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \quad \dots (5)$$

For the analysis of the flow state with the die pre-heated, the temperature distribution in the material should be described. For this purpose, the following energy equation is used as a basic equation on an assumption that the composite materials are homogeneous and isotropic as far as the thermal nature is concerned,

$$\rho c \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + V_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + V_y \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) - k \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) = 0, \quad \dots (6)$$

where T is the temperature, k is the thermal conductivity, Vx and Vy are the velocity component in x and y direction respectively, ρ is the density, c is the specific heat and t is the time. Using the temperature distribution obtained by Eq.(6), the viscosity coefficient μ(ε̇, T) which depends on the temperature is defined as follows;

$$\mu(\dot{\epsilon}, T) = \mu(\dot{\epsilon}) \cdot \mu(T), \quad \dots (7)$$

where ε̇ denotes the strain rate. μ(T) can be written as,

$$\mu(T) = \exp[\beta(T_0 - T)], \quad \dots (8)$$

where T₀ is the room temperature, and β is the material constant. μ(ε̇, T) can be rewritten as,

$$\mu(\dot{\epsilon}, T) = \mu(\dot{\epsilon}) \cdot \exp[\beta(T_0 - T)], \quad \dots (9)$$

2-2 Numerical analysis

Much attention has been paid to the anisotropy of the viscosity. In the initial state the principal axis of the anisotropy was accorded with X direction and in the second step and thereafter it was accorded with direction of the velocity vectors in the previous step. The initial state analysis was made on the model shown in Fig. 1-(a), and the second step was analyzed on the model shown in Fig.1-(b). To the additional elements the viscosity coefficient which is based on the velocity vectors of the entrance of the rib in the previous step. The numerical analysis was undertaken by adding the element step by step.

Taking into consideration the molding temperature, the flow state was analyzed by the method described above, i.e. first the temperature distribution was determined and then the viscosity coefficient and finally the velocity vectors were determined. The process was repeated.

For the numerical analysis the method of weighted residual of Galerkin and Newton-Raphson method were used as described in the previous paper. The shape function is a quadratic function of u and v and a linear function of p, and the element used was triangular with six nodes. To solve the energy equation, the same method as described above was used for space integration and Crank-Nicholson formulation was used for time integration. In this case, shape function was a linear function and the element used was triangular with three nodes.

As a model system a T-shaped canal with the surface cavity and the resin-rich at the rib corner was chosen. In Figs.1 and 2 the finite element models for the system are shown. The models given in Figs.1-(a) and (b) are those with the corner radius of the die Rf=0mm, while in the models given in Figs.2-(a) and (b) Rf≠0mm. The canals given in Figs.1-(a) and 2-(b) were used to analyze the initial flow state during the molding process and those given in Figs.1-(b) and 2-(b) were used to study the flow state with the rib wall effect.

The lines A-E and A-E-E' in the figures are symmetrical axis, A-B is the surface of the punch, B-C-D is the inner surface of the die and D-E and D'-E' are the entrance into the rib.

The boundary conditions for these models are as follows; the velocity of the press stroke on the line A-B is $V_y=0.3\text{mm/sec}$, the lines E-D and E'-D' are a free surface, the line B-C is a non-frictional boundary and the line D-C is a frictional boundary except the point D. The boundary conditions for the temperature distribution are as follows; the molding temperature on the lines A-B, B-C and C-D in Figs. 1 and 2 in given and the lines A-E, E-D and E'-D' is an adiabatic boundary.

Fig. 1 Finite element model in the case of $R_f=0\text{mm}$.

Fig. 2 Finite element model in the case of $R_f=0\text{mm}$.

3) Numerical results

In Figs. 3 to 6 the velocities of the flow determined from the numerical solutions are shown. The material constants used for the calculation were $K_T=6.77\text{N}\cdot\text{s}/\text{mm}^2$ (the pseudo-plastic viscosity) and $n=0.496$ (the power exponent). These constants were obtained by the experiments. The anisotropy constant was $K_T/K_L=3$.

In Fig.3-(a), it is seen that the initial flow state goes around at the rib corner and has a tendency to flow slightly upward over the horizontal direction. In the second step shown in Fig.3-(b) the flow at the rib entrance was found to have a tendency to proceed to the rib wall. The flow state shown in Fig.3-(c), resulted in the meander through the corner into the rib, though it is relatively gentle. Moreover, it was observed that there is the velocity vector which shows the upward flow at the rib part.

In Fig.4, the cases with the corner radius of $R_f=0\text{mm}$ are shown. From comparison between Fig.3 and Fig.4 both of which are the cases of $R_f=0\text{mm}$, it was found that the flow goes around at the rib corner and meander flow in the rib part is weakened. The horizontal velocity components near the central surface part seem to have a tendency of decreasing compared with Fig. 3-(c) during the final stage of the molding process. The central cavity appears to be caused by the phenomenon.

Fig.3 Velocity vectors calculated in the case of $Rf=0mm$.
 ($n=0.496$, $K_T/K_L=3$)

Fig.4 Velocity vectors calculated in the case of $Rf \neq 0$ mm.
 ($n=0.496$, $K_T/K_L=3$)

In Figs.5 and 6, the calculated velocity vectors and temperature distribution are shown. In these cases, the material constants, n, K_I and K_T/K_L are same as those of BMC which are given above. The thermal material constants used for the calculation, were as follows; in Eq.(9) the basic temperature ($T_0=20^\circ\text{C}$) and $\beta=0.020$ in Eq.(6), the thermal conductivity $k=0.02$ kcal/ N°C specific heat is $c=0.2$ kcal/ Kg°C . The molding temperature was at 80°C and the time interval between setting the materials in the pre-heated die and starting compression was 30 sec.

Fig. 5 Calculated temperature distribution.
 ($k=0.4$ kcal/ mh°C)

Fig. 6 Velocity vectors calculated considering the effect of the molding temperature.
 ($n=0.496$, $K_T/K_L=3$, $\beta=0.020$)

The temperature distribution of the initial state in Fig.5-(a) shows that the surface lamina is close to 80°C and that there is a temperature difference between the surface and inner laminae. In Fig.6-(a) the initial flow state in which the viscosity is affected by the temperature distribution shows that the velocity vectors go around the rib corner and upper part of the rib shoulder. The nature in the flow state obtained here is same as that of Fig.3-(a) except that the upper surface lamina is moving greatly toward the symmetric axis and the vectors in the middle which only go to the horizontal direction are larger.

In Figs.5-(b) and 5-(c) it is seen that the temperature distribution approaches to the uniform state as the step advances so that the flow states resemble to those given in Figs.3-(b) and (c). However, the upward flow was seen to be present at the rib shoulder and the plane part in every step of the molding and, moreover, the flow at the rib part was gentle and the meander flow was not observed.

4) Experimental analysis

To check the validity of the numerical solutions, the experimental analysis was carried out and compared with the numerical results.

4-1 Experimental method

Experiment was made in the same manner as described in the previous paper. It is summarized as follows; in order to characterize the flow properties of BMC, linear colored marks made of the same materials were buried in each lamina at a definite interval to obtain finite displacement vectors by measuring the location of marks before and after the molding process and deformation state diagrams were drawn from the state of each lamina. Throughout the measurements the molding temperature was 80°C at which no rapid polymerization of the materials could occur.

4-2 Experimental results

The finite displacement vectors obtained from the experimental analysis carried out at room temperature had already been shown in the previous paper. In Figs.7 and 8 in this paper, the finite displacement vectors and deformation diagrams are shown, respectively, both being obtained from the experiments carried out at 80°C. Figs.7-(a) to (c) are of the case where the corner radius of the die, $R_f=0\text{mm}$, while $R_f=6\text{mm}$ in the models given in Figs.7-(d) to (e). AS for the step in the molding process, Figs.7-(a),(d) and 8-(a) are designated to be the step R1, Figs.7-(b),(e) and 8-(b) to be the step R2 and Figs.7-(c),(f) and 8-(c) to be the step R3 and the corresponding rib lengths were set to be 12mm, 24mm and 36mm, respectively.

From Figs.7 and 8, it can be seen that the flow states that go around the rib corner and upward toward the rib shoulder are same as those obtained from the experiments at room temperature except that the surface lamina moves toward the symmetric axis and large displacement vectors appear in the middle. As for the effects of the corner radius of the die, the material flow going around the rib corner is remarkable in the case of $R_f=0\text{mm}$.

5) Discussion

The flow states during the compression molding process have been analyzed by using the progressive step by step method. The results of numerical solution were found to agree with the experimental results better than the previous paper.

It is obvious that the characteristics in the flow states of BMC such as the flow going around the rib corner, the upward flow at the rib shoulder and the meander flow in the rib canal are caused by the anisotropic nature in the orientation of glass fiber involved in the materials. It appears that an anisotropic nature in the flow states observed on the die with $R_f=0\text{mm}$ (Fig. 3) is effective strongly to prevent the formulation of the surface cavity, although the brittle weakness occurs in

Fig. 7 Finite displacement vectors in the case of molding temperature 80°C .

Fig. 7 Finite displacement vectors in the case of molding temperature 80°C .

Fig. 8 Diagram of deformation state in the case of molding temperature 80°C.
(L) Horizontal (R) Vertical section.

the bottom part of the fin. In contrast, the anisotropic nature in the flow with die of $Rf=0mm$ is effective weakly and the surface cavity might be produced in the canal. Thus it is unable to conquer the trouble with the die of this type and other conditions are required for further improvements.

The numerical results obtained for the models with the die pre-heated (Fig. 6) were found to be in good agreement with the experimental results (Figs. 7 and 8); the surface lamina has a tendency to move toward the symmetric axis and large vectors appear in the middle lamina. In Figs. 9 and 10, the velocity vectors obtained for the models with $\beta=0.030$ and 0.035 are shown. In these cases, the decrease in viscosity with the rise of temperature is much more than that found for the material with $\beta=0.020$.

The flow states of the surface and middle lamina given in Figs. 9 and 10 are quite similar to those in Fig. 6-(a), but the upward flow is remarkable at the rib shoulder. These results indicate that the decrease in the viscosity may have the same effect as that caused by the strong anisotropic nature. Moreover, regarding the effect of temperature distribution, larger the temperature difference between the surface and the middle lamina, more similar the flow states to that the strong anisotropic nature.

Accordingly, the formulation of the surface cavity may be depressed by the use of materials which show the much decrease in viscosity with the temperature rise and also by the quick start of compression after locating the materials in the pre-heated die.

Fig. 9 Velocity vectors calculated considering the effect of the molding temperature. ($\beta=0.030$)

Fig. 10 Velocity vectors calculated considering the effect of the molding temperature. ($\beta=0.035$)

6) Conclusion

In order to obtain fundamental data applicable to the improvement in the design of molding die the flow state of composite materials during the molding process have been numerically analyzed by assuming the anisotropy of the flow. The numerical results obtained by the progressive step by step method in this paper were found to be in good agreement with the experimental results for the canals with the rib wall. It was concluded that the flow characteristics of the composite materials are influenced by the orientation of glass fibers during the molding process. The flow state around the corner during the molding process depends strongly on an anisotropic characteristic of the flow for the composite materials. These phenomena were discussed and should be controlled by applying more stronger anisotropic nature or by changing the charge pattern of the object for further improvements.

Moreover, the effect of the molding temperature was studied by introducing the equation for heat conduction to the governing equations and the numerical analysis was made at a temperature where no polymerization could occur in the materials. It was found that the flow properties of the materials with much decrease coefficient in the viscosity and with a large temperature difference in the surface and the middle lamina are very similar to those having the strong anisotropic nature.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Japan Catalytic Chemical Industry Co Ltd, Japan, for providing some of the materials.

References

- 1.) Hirai, T, and Katayama, T; Proc. of the 1978 Int. Conf. on Composite Materials, 1283 (1978)
- 2.) V.P. Pervadchuk and V.I. Yankov; Heat Transfer-Soviet Research, 10, 1, 11 (1978)
- 3.) F.A. Myers and J.M. Maxel; Tech. Proc. 33rd Annual Conf. SPI 19-D (1978)